

Development of a Fully-RMC R2S Shutdown Dose Rate Calculation Framework

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DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.20804008

ABSTRACT

A fully integrated Rigorous Two-Step (R2S) calculation framework has been developed within the Reactor Monte Carlo code (RMC) to perform self-consistent neutron transport, activation analysis, decay-photon generation, and shutdown dose-rate calculation on a single platform. This framework is achieved by coupling various RMC modules and incorporates several new features, notably the extension of the existing criticality transport–depletion coupling framework to a fixed-source transport–activation coupling framework and the development of a dedicated decay-photon source generation module. Verification studies were conducted using a simple shielding problem with corresponding activation schemes, assessing the accuracy of the fully RMC-based R2S workflow and its new features against results from OpenMC. The first case, which compared nuclide inventories, confirmed the newly implemented fixed-source transport–activation coupling framework, showing excellent agreement between RMC and OpenMC. The second case successfully verified the decay-photon spectrum generation and dose-rate calculation, with RMC results showing good consistency with OpenMC in both spectral patterns and total dose-rate values, and relative differences for the total dose rates all below 0.5%. These verification results collectively demonstrate the correctness and reliability of the implementation, confirming that the fully-RMC R2S framework provides an efficient and reliable solution for shutdown dose-rate calculation and significantly enhances the overall applicability of RMC to advanced fusion neutronics simulations.

Keywords: Monte Carlo, Fusion Neutronics, R2S, RMC, Shutdown Dose Rate

1. INTRODUCTION

Nuclear fusion is widely recognized as a promising clean and sustainable energy source that has attracted growing global attention in recent years. Compared with fission systems, fusion reactors exhibit distinctly different neutron characteristics. In tokamak devices, deuterium–tritium (D–T) fusion reactions release approximately 17.6 MeV of energy per event, producing high-energy neutrons with an average energy of 14.1 MeV and significantly higher flux levels. These high-energy neutrons can cause severe damage and degradation to structural materials, while also generating radioactive nuclides through neutron activation reactions. After reactor shutdown, the decay of these nuclides emits residual radiation, posing potential radiological hazards to maintenance personnel. Therefore, accurate shutdown dose rate (SDR) calculations are essential for ensuring the safe design, operation, and maintenance of fusion facilities.

In fusion neutronics, Monte Carlo codes play a crucial role by providing key capabilities such as large-scale modeling of complex reactor geometries, variance reduction techniques for deep penetration shielding, fixed-source simulations for neutron behavior in fusion environments, and tally functions for recording quantities such as energy spectra and energy deposition during neutron transport.[1]

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Monte Carlo–based shutdown dose rate (SDR) calculations generally adopt two main approaches: the Direct One-Step (D1S) method [2] and the Rigorous Two-Step (R2S) method [3]. The D1S method assumes that radioactive nuclides emit decay photons during irradiation, enabling simultaneous neutron and photon transport within a single Monte Carlo simulation. In contrast, the R2S method separates neutron transport and activation calculations to explicitly determine decay photon sources, thereby achieving higher accuracy. Owing to this improved precision, the R2S method is widely preferred for complex nuclear systems.

Several institutions have developed R2S-based SDR systems using Monte Carlo codes. In 2002, under the ITER project, the Institute of Plasma Physics, Chinese Academy of Sciences, developed an R2S system coupling MCNP with FISPACT, achieving the first full 3D SDR calculation validated through ITER experiments [3]. Subsequently, in 2012, Germany’s Karlsruhe Institute of Technology (KIT) established the R2Smesh system, which improved neutron flux and spectrum calculations through the use of non-uniform meshes [4]. Later, in 2016, the European R2SUNED program coupled MCNP with ACAB for mesh-based SDR analysis, introducing homogenization techniques [5]. More recently, in 2021, Dr. Zhang Xian from North China Electric Power University developed the cosRMC–ALARA R2S system for SDR calculations [6]. In 2024, OpenMC team further advanced this field by developing a fully OpenMC-based R2S implementation, marking the first realization of the complete SDR workflow using a single Monte Carlo code.[7, 8]

The Reactor Monte Carlo code (RMC) [9, 10] is a mature Monte Carlo particle transport code developed by the Reactor Engineering Analysis Laboratory (REAL) at the Department of Engineering Physics, Tsinghua University. RMC possesses all the essential capabilities required for fusion neutronics studies, including advanced transport algorithms, large-scale modeling capabilities, burnup and depletion calculations, and variance reduction techniques.[11, 12] These features provide a solid foundation for implementing a fully-RMC R2S SDR calculation framework.

The motivation for developing a fully RMC-based R2S SDR framework arises not only from software licensing constraints but also from the potential loss of accuracy during data transfer between different codes. Moreover, such an integrated framework offers greater flexibility, user-friendliness, and extensibility for future internal development. Since OpenMC has demonstrated the feasibility of completing the entire SDR workflow within a single code[8], our goal is to establish a fully RMC-based R2S SDR calculation framework by leveraging RMC’s existing capabilities and incorporating newly developed features to fully realize the R2S methodology.

2. FULLY-RMC R2S METHODOLOGY AND NEW FEATURE IMPLEMENTATION

The framework of the R2S system implemented in RMC is illustrated in the Figure 1. According to the calculation scenario, the neutron transport module first performs neutron transport simulations to obtain reaction rate data, which are then transferred to DEPTH—the burnup and activation module of RMC[13]—to compute the nuclide densities of activated materials. In this stage, RMC conducts a coupled transport–activation calculation based on predefined activation schemes and outputs the nuclide densities of activated materials for each activation step. Subsequently, the decay-photon generation module calculates the decay-photon spectra using the activation results. Finally, the decay-photon source and its corresponding source strength are used as input for the photon transport calculation. Based on the tally functions, photon flux distributions are obtained and converted into dose-rate data through flux-to-dose conversion factors.

This R2S framework follows a similar structure to those developed by other institutions. However, to fully realize the R2S methodology within RMC, several new features must be developed. These include extending the existing criticality transport–depletion coupling framework to support fixed-source scenarios commonly required for SDR calculations, developing a dedicated decay-photon generation module, and establishing a fully integrated coupling framework for the first step of the R2S process.

Figure 1. Fully-RMC R2S SDR Coupling Framework.

2.1. Fixed-Source Transport–Activation Coupling Framework

The overall framework of RMC burnup and activation calculations is illustrated in Figure 2, where the newly developed fixed-source transport–activation coupling framework is highlighted. This extension complements the existing criticality–depletion calculation mode, providing a unified and complete framework for both approaches.

Figure 2. RMC Burnup and Activation Calculations Framework.

To further support activation scenarios, a new source-rate activation mode has been developed within the fixed-source depletion framework, allowing users to directly specify the neutron source strength for activation analyses. This mode is particularly well suited for simulating activation processes in shielding analyses and fusion applications.

It should be noted that most existing R2S frameworks perform only a single neutron transport simulation at the beginning of the workflow to determine flux and reaction rate distributions, which are then used repeatedly for all activation steps. This approach provides sufficient accuracy while significantly reducing computational cost. RMC, however, currently supports only the fully coupled approach, in which neutron transport and activation are performed sequentially at each step to ensure higher consistency between neutron field and material composition.

2.2. Decay-Photon Source Generation Module

The implementation of the Decay-Photon Source Generation Module relies on spectrum data from nuclear data libraries. The decay photon data were obtained from the decay sublibrary files of ENDF/B-

III.0 (MF=8, MT=457)[14]. For each nuclide, the number of photons emitted in energy group E_g is given by:

$$I_{E_g,i} = V \sum_{E_g \leq E_j < E_{g+1}} I_{E_j,i} N_i \lambda_i \quad (1)$$

where $I_{E_j,i}$ is the number of photons emitted at discrete energy E_j (provided by the data library), N_i is the nuclide density, V is the volume of material cell and λ_i is the decay constant of nuclide i . Based on this expression, the decay-photon spectrum of each nuclide can be obtained. By summing the contributions from all nuclides, the total decay-photon spectrum of the activated material for group g is expressed as:

$$S_\gamma(E_g) = \sum_{k=1}^n I_{E_g,k} \quad (2)$$

In RMC, the photon energy group structure can either be user-defined or automatically determined by the code. It should be noted that the nuclear data library provides both discrete and continuous photon spectra. Since the contribution from continuous spectra is generally small, only discrete photon data are currently considered in RMC. The decay-photon spectrum generation function in RMC can be applied in two modes: (1) coupled with the transport-activation framework for complex scenarios requiring detailed transport calculations, and (2) in point-depletion mode for simplified activation analyses.

3. VERIFICATION OF THE R2S FRAMEWORK AND ITS NEW FEATURES

This study includes verification of the newly developed features, including the fixed-source activation calculation, decay-photon generation, and the fully-RMC R2S framework for dose-rate calculation.

3.1. Verification Approach and Nuclear Data Libraries

In this verification work, OpenMC is selected for comparison, as it has been validated in numerous studies and has demonstrated strong performance in fusion neutronics analyses as well as R2S SDR calculations [8]. For transport calculations, the ENDF/B-VIII.0 nuclear data library is used in both RMC and OpenMC. For burnup calculations in RMC, the default library is DepthMainLib, generated using data from ORIGEN2 and ORIGEN-S [13]. Additionally, a new burnup data library based on ENDF/B-VIII.0 [14] has been adopted, containing updated depletion chains, decay data, and decay-photon spectra. In this verification, the ENDF/B-VIII.0-based library is used in RMC for both depletion chain and decay-photon spectrum generation. Correspondingly, OpenMC is configured with the ENDF/B-VIII.0-based depletion chain XML file (thermal spectrum) to ensure consistent depletion and decay data between the two codes.

3.2. Verification of the Fixed-Source Transport-Activation Coupling Framework

To verify the fixed-source transport-activation calculations, a simple activation case 1 was constructed, as illustrated in Figure 3. The case 1 model consists of two concentric cubes: an inner cube with a side length of 20 cm and an outer cube with a side length of 30 cm, forming an inner region and a surrounding shell region. The inner cube is filled with 304 stainless steel (71% Fe, 19% Cr, 9% Ni, and 1% Mn), while the shell region is filled with water.

For the activation scenario, a 14 MeV neutron source with a strength of 1×10^{10} neutrons/s was placed at the center of the Case 1 model. Four activation steps were performed, each with a duration of 20 days, and 1×10^6 neutron histories were simulated for both codes. The nuclide production results obtained using RMC were then compared with those from OpenMC. The total nuclide inventories at each time step are summarized in Table I. Several important nuclides were selected for comparison,

Figure 3. Verification case models.

including Co-60, Mn-54, Fe-55, and Ni-63. The results show that RMC agrees closely with OpenMC for all nuclides, with relative differences below 0.2% for Co-60, Mn-54, and Fe-55, and below 0.8% for Ni-63. These findings confirm the accuracy of the fixed-source transport–activation coupling framework implemented in RMC.

Table I. Comparison of nuclide inventories between RMC and OpenMC.

Co-60				Fe-55			
Time Step (days)	RMC ($\times 10^{24}$ atoms)	OpenMC ($\times 10^{24}$ atoms)	Rel. Diff.	Time Step (days)	RMC ($\times 10^{24}$ atoms)	OpenMC ($\times 10^{24}$ atoms)	Rel. Diff.
20	3.67E-11	3.67E-11	0.10%	20	2.66E-09	2.66E-09	0.07%
40	7.31E-11	7.32E-11	-0.16%	40	5.29E-09	5.30E-09	-0.13%
60	1.09E-10	1.09E-10	-0.12%	60	7.88E-09	7.89E-09	-0.11%
80	1.45E-10	1.45E-10	-0.15%	80	1.04E-08	1.04E-08	-0.14%
Mn-54				Ni-63			
Time Step (days)	RMC ($\times 10^{24}$ atoms)	OpenMC ($\times 10^{24}$ atoms)	Rel. Diff.	Time Step (days)	RMC ($\times 10^{24}$ atoms)	OpenMC ($\times 10^{24}$ atoms)	Rel. Diff.
20	2.47E-10	2.47E-10	0.14%	20	4.81E-11	4.80E-11	0.19%
40	4.84E-10	4.85E-10	-0.16%	40	9.62E-11	9.55E-11	0.75%
60	7.10E-10	7.11E-10	-0.10%	60	1.44E-10	1.43E-10	0.74%
80	9.26E-10	9.28E-10	-0.13%	80	1.92E-10	1.91E-10	0.55%

3.3. Verification of Decay-Photon Spectrum Generation

For the verification of decay photon generation and dose-rate calculations, a slightly more complex cuboid model case 2 with multiple activation regions was constructed, as shown in Figure 3. The cuboid has dimensions of 20 cm \times 20 cm \times 10 cm and consists of six cells containing two types of materials. Cells 1, 3, and 5 were filled with stainless steel, while cells 2 and 4 were filled with water; cell 6 was modeled as void. A 14 MeV neutron point source was placed at position (5, 15, 5), corresponding to the center of cell 6.

In this scenario, four activation steps were performed using fully coupled transport–activation and decay-photon generation calculations in both RMC and OpenMC, with 1×10^7 neutron histories simulated for each code. The total irradiation duration was 15 days, with source rates set to $[1 \times 10^{10}, 1 \times 10^{10}, 2.5 \times 10^{10}, 2.5 \times 10^{10}]$ neutrons/s and time steps of [3.5, 1.5, 5, 5] days, respectively.

The decay-photon spectra obtained at the final activation step were used for comparison. Figure 4 shows the decay-photon spectra of the steel cells (cells 1, 3, and 5), with 15 energy bins defined for the

spectrum, while Figure 5 presents the spectra of the water cells (cells 2 and 4), with 10 energy bins. The RMC results show excellent agreement with those from OpenMC, with only a difference observed in the water cells between 1 and 2 MeV. Overall, the spectra exhibit consistent patterns and comparable magnitudes, confirming the reliability of the decay photon generation implementations in RMC.

Figure 4. Comparison of decay-photon spectra in steel cells (Cells 1,3 and 5).

Figure 5. Comparison of decay-photon spectra in water cells (Cells 2 and 4).

3.4. Verification of Dose Rate Calculation

Based on the verification of decay photon generation, the decay photon data were converted into photon source inputs for photon transport calculations, representing the second step of the R2S workflow. In the photon source definition, five different cell-based sources were specified. The source strength corresponds to the total photon intensity, while the energy distribution is defined using a discrete distribution, where the photon energy values and their corresponding intensities—representing the probability of each energy—are directly calculated and output from the photon generation module without binning. A total of 1×10^8 photon histories were simulated in both RMC and OpenMC, and the thick-target bremsstrahlung (TTB) approximation was considered.

For the photon flux and dose rate calculations, a 2×2 mesh tally was defined to cover the entire model, with each mesh element measuring $10 \text{ cm} \times 10 \text{ cm} \times 10 \text{ cm}$, as shown in Figure 3, Case 2(Mesh). Photon fluxes were obtained using the mesh tally, and dose rates were calculated by applying the ICRP-119 flux-to-dose conversion factors.[15]. The dose-rate spectra of the four meshes calculated by RMC and OpenMC are shown in Figure 6, while the total dose-rate values for each mesh are summarized in the table II.

Both the spectral and tabulated results show excellent agreement between RMC and OpenMC for the dose-rate calculations. The only exception occurs in the photon energy range below 0.01 MeV, where differences arise, possibly due to the divergence in photon interaction data or slight variations in physics models for low-energy transport between the two codes. As for the total dose rates, relative differences

Figure 6. Dose rate spectra of the four meshes calculated by RMC and OpenMC.

Table II. Total dose rate comparison between RMC and OpenMC.

Mesh	RMC Dose Rate (Sv/h)	OpenMC Dose Rate (Sv/h)	Rel. Diff.
1	4.70E-03	4.69E-03	0.25%
2	2.80E-03	2.78E-03	0.50%
3	1.74E-03	1.74E-03	0.03%
4	4.70E-03	4.71E-03	-0.23%

remain below 0.5% for all meshes, demonstrating the correctness of the RMC R2S framework and its newly implemented features.

4. CONCLUSIONS AND FUTURE WORK

This work presents the development of a fully-RMC R2S calculation framework, along with the implementation and verification of newly developed features essential for completing the R2S workflow, including the fixed-source transport-activation coupling framework and the decay photon generation module. The framework was verified using two simplified shielding cases, with OpenMC serving as the reference code. The results demonstrate excellent agreement between RMC and OpenMC, confirming the correctness and reliability of the implementation.

For future work, more complex benchmark problems, including demonstrations of variance reduction capabilities, will be studied, and the fully RMC-based R2S framework will be further validated against existing reference results. A simplified transport-activation scheme, using a single neutron transport calculation to provide fluxes and reaction rates for all activation steps, will be developed as an alternative to the fully coupled approach. In addition, a mesh-based R2S scheme will be explored. Further efforts will focus on enhancing the user-friendliness and extensibility of the internally coupled framework by streamlining the definition and execution of calculation modules.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

This work was supported by the National Natural Science Foundation of China (Grant No. W2542003).

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